

Synthesis of 2-Thio-3-aryl-5-alkyltetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines

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Although interaction of aldehydes and amines in presence of carbon disulphide was known earlier¹⁻⁴, the constitution of these products was first conclusively proved by Ainley *et al.*⁵. The products were assigned the formula 2-thio-3,5-disubstituted-tetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines. It has also been shown by these authors that if two amines are used in the condensation, the aryl group enters 3-position but the alkyl group enters 5-position. Rieche *et al.*⁶ synthesised some such 1,3,5-thiadiazines, among which 2-thio-3,5-di- β -phenethyltetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine was found to exhibit considerable bactericidal, fungicidal, and virostatic activities.

With this view it was thought of interest to synthesise various 1,3,5-thiadiazines with different substituents at 3- and 5-position and vary them systematically in the hope to obtain bacteriostatic compounds. It is worthy to note that these compounds also contain the isothiocyanate (NCS) moiety, which brings about bacteriostatic activity in the molecule⁷.

Synthesis of 3,5-Dialkyl/diaryl-2-thio-tetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines.—To a cooled methanolic or aqueous methanolic solution of the appropriate amine (0.2*M*) was added with stirring CS₂ (0.1*M*). This solution was stirred for 1 hr., cooled to 5° in an ice bath, and while stirring formaldehyde solution (0.2*M*) was added during 30 min. After stirring for 1 hr. more, the solution was warmed on a water bath for few minutes when a product separated. After washing it with ice-water several times, it was crystallised from excess of aqueous ethanol. All these compounds crystallise in colorless needles or platelets; yield 60-65%. Table I describes the compounds prepared.

Synthesis of 2-Thio-3-aryl-5-alkyltetrahydro-1,3,5-thiadiazines.—A stirred mixture of aromatic amine (0.1*M*), CS₂ (0.1*M*), and water (100 ml) was treated during 30 min. at the room temperature with an aliphatic amine (0.1*M*). After stirring this mixture for 2 hr., it was diluted to 2 litres, filtered from little insoluble matter, and the filtrate after cooling to 5° was treated with formaldehyde solution (0.2*M*). On stirring this mixture further for 1 hr., a solid product separated, which was washed several times with

1. Hlasiwetz, *Ber.*, 1872, 5, 803.
 2. Claus, *Ber.*, 1872, 5, 382.
 3. Mulder, *Annalen*, 1873, 166, 228.
 4. Levi, *Gazzetta*, 1931, 61, 803.
 5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 147.
 6. Rieche, *Pharm. Z.*, 1960, 293, 957.
 7. Garmaise and McKay, *Canad. Pat.* 579233/1959; *Chem. Abst.*, 1960, 54, 412.
- N.B. All melting points are uncorrected.

cold water. It was crystallised from excess aqueous ethanol; average yield 55 to 60%. All these compounds are colorless needles or platelets. Compounds, thus prepared, are described in Table II.

TABLE I

R = R'.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.
Et	66°	C ₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	33.5	33.7
n-Bu	84°/20mm	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	25.0	26.0
n-C ₃ H ₁₁	103°	C ₁₃ H ₂₆ N ₂ S ₂	23.4	23.4
n-C ₆ H ₁₃	145°	C ₁₅ H ₃₀ N ₂ S ₂	21.0	21.2
Ph	140°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	22.4	22.4
o-ClC ₆ H ₄	237°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂	18.0	18.0
p-ClC ₆ H ₄	138°	"	17.6	18.0
2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	140°	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ Cl ₄ S ₂	14.8	15.1
o-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	103°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	20.1	20.4
p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	200°	"	20.0	20.4
o-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	110°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	18.8	18.5
p-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	163°	"	18.3	18.5
p-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	130°	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	16.6	17.0
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	102°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	20.1	20.4

TABLE II

R'.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
A. R = aniline.					B. R = p-chloroaniline.			
Me	148°	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂	29.2	28.6	139°	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	24.5	24.7
Et	106°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	26.8	26.9	110-11°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	23.1	23.5
n-Bu	101°	C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	23.8	24.0	110°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	21.1	21.3
n-C ₃ H ₁₁	111°	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂	22.6	22.9	105-106°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	20.0	20.3
n-C ₆ H ₁₃	108°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	21.7	21.8	117°	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	19.4	19.5
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	151°	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	21.0	21.3	126°/30mm	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	19.0	19.1
C. R = p-anisidine.					D. R = benzylamine.			
Me	161°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S ₂	25.2	25.2	92°	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	26.6	26.9
Et	190°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S ₂	23.8	23.9	110°	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	25.1	25.4
n-Bu	195°	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ ON ₂ S ₂	21.5	21.6	100°	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂	22.7	22.9
n-C ₃ H ₁₁	188°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ ON ₂ S ₂	20.2	20.6	110°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	21.5	21.8
n-C ₆ H ₁₃	197-98°	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ ON ₂ S ₂	19.7	20.0	100°	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₂	20.5	20.8
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	153°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S ₂	19.0.	19.4	102°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	20.0	20.4

TABLE IIA

R'.	Formula.	%S reqd.	R= <i>o</i> -toluidine.		R= <i>m</i> -toluidine.		R= <i>p</i> -toluidine.	
			M.P.	%S found.	M.P.	%S found.	M.P.	%S found.
CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂	26.9	113°	26.6	98°/25mm	26.4	117°	26.6
C ₂ H ₅	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	25.4	98°	25.3	98°	25.0	194°	25.4
<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂	22.9	109°	22.8	109°	22.9	105°	28.6
<i>n</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	21.8	114°	21.5	106°	21.6	117°	21.5
<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₂	20.8	116°	20.6	130°	20.3	105°	20.6
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	20.4	99°	20.0	102°	20.0	139°	20.2

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